

ThirdEye Data

AI Image Processing System

For the Energy Sector

AI-Powered Computer Vision for Electric Pole
Inspection & Infrastructure Intelligence

Business Goals & Challenges

- ✓ Major utility serving 14M+ customers across 50,000+ sq miles
- ✓ Massive drone image volumes with poor quality impacting analytics reliability
- ✓ Slow manual validation & difficulty reading utility pole tags from images
- ✓ Goal: AI platform for automated image quality validation & defect detection

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AI-Powered Image Processing Pipeline

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Intelligent Image Processing Features

Drone Image Ingestion

Seamlessly ingests high-volume drone-captured inspection images for processing

AI Quality Assessment

AI models evaluate each image for clarity, exposure, and inspection suitability

Blur Detection

Automatically flags and filters blurry images to ensure downstream accuracy

Occlusion Detection

Detects obstructions blocking utility pole components in inspection images

Intelligent Image Processing Features

Camera Angle Validation

Validates drone capture angles to ensure optimal image geometry for reliable inspection

Pole Tag Detection & OCR

Automatically detects & extracts utility pole ID tags using advanced OCR recognition

Pole Structure Analysis

AI analyzes electric pole structure integrity and flags structural deviations automatically

Anomaly Detection Routing

Routes only quality-validated images to downstream anomaly detection engine

Business Impact

Automated Image Validation

Eliminates manual review of thousands of drone-captured inspection images.

Higher Inspection Accuracy

Only top-quality images enter defect detection, improving reliability.

Faster Infrastructure Analysis

Speeds up asset inspection workflows across large utility networks.

Scalable Utility Intelligence

Supports large-scale drone inspection programs across 50,000+ square miles.

Technology Stack

Step 1

Drone Cameras →
Image Acquisition

Step 2

Computer Vision &
Quality Analysis

Step 3

OCR & Tag
Recognition

Step 4

Analytics
Dashboard &
Utility Operations

Thankyou!

ThirdEye Data

Advanced Infrastructure Intelligence

For more information, Please visit:
[Image Processing System](#)